

REPORT CARD 2026

INFECTIOUS DISEASES – PART 1: CYTOMEGALOVIRUS (CMV) AND THE CHALLENGES OF CONGENITAL INFECTION

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Journal of
**Hearing
Science**

MEDINCUS

INFECTIOUS DISEASES - PART 1: CYTOMEGALOVIRUS (CMV) AND THE CHALLENGES OF CONGENITAL INFECTION

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We begin a series of bulletins on **“INFECTIOUS DISEASES”**. This bulletin will address the most common infectious agent, Cytomegalovirus, which causes congenital hearing loss. We invite you to join us on this journey about infectious diseases.

THE INFECTIOUS AGENT - CYTOMEGALOVIRUS

Cytomegalovirus (CMV) belongs to the Herpesviridae family, a large group of viruses characterized primarily by the ability to establish latent and recurrent infections throughout the host's lifetime. CMV is the most frequent congenital infection in humans, with an estimated seroprevalence of about 60% of the adult population in developed countries and more than 90% in developing countries (Griffiths, Reeves, 2021).

In immunocompetent individuals, the infection is usually controlled by an effective immune response, and is often asymptomatic or associated with mild clinical manifestations. However, in situations where the immune system is compromised, CMV can replicate intensely and cause severe disease with target organ impairment. From a structural point of view, these viruses have a viral envelope, and are therefore classified as enveloped viruses. The envelope is formed by a bilayer of phospholipids and proteins meaning that, when in contact with agents such as detergent, 70% alcohol, or acids the envelope is dissolved and the virus is inactivated.

BUT WHAT IS THIS ENVELOPE?

The envelope is formed by a phospholipid bilayer and proteins that, when exposed to external agents such as detergent, 70% alcohol, and acids, is dissolved, which means the virus can be inactivated.

ROUTES OF TRANSMISSION AND INFECTION BY CYTOMEGALOVIRUS THROUGHOUT LIFE

CMV infection can occur at different times of life and is characterized by its wide dissemination in the human population. Transmission of the virus occurs predominantly through direct contact with infected bodily fluids, including:

- saliva;
- urine;
- respiratory secretions;
- cervicovaginal; secretions;
- semen;
- breast milk;
- blood.

After exposure, the virus begins its replicative cycle in the host's body, and may establish a primary infection or reinfection by different viral strains.

From a clinical and virological point of view, productive CMV infections can manifest in three main forms, namely:

1st form: corresponds to the primary infection, which occurs when a previously seronegative individual comes into contact with the virus for the first time.

2nd form: refers to reinfection, characterized by exposure to a new viral strain, even in the presence of previously established immunity.

3rd form: involves the reactivation of the latent virus, a frequent phenomenon after the resolution of the primary infection, when CMV remains persistent in cellular reservoirs and can replicate again under certain physiological or immunological conditions.

TRANSMISSION ROUTES

The spread of CMV can occur through different routes, reflecting its wide capacity for transmission between individuals. Among the main forms of transmission are:

- contaminated blood transfusion;
- organ or tissue transplantation;
- vertical transmission, especially in the form of congenital infection, when the virus is transmitted from mother to fetus during pregnancy;
- sexual contact;
- direct contact with oral or respiratory secretions.

Vertical transmission is particularly relevant clinically, since it is associated with several congenital manifestations and represents an important cause of childhood morbidity.

As a result of its mode of spread, the virus can be present in more than 50% of the adult population, although it rarely causes serious symptoms in healthy people. As mentioned, the real danger lies in vulnerable populations and their immune systems, since viral replication can result in significant clinical complications.

Among the most severe manifestations associated with active CMV infection are:

- **retinitis**, which can lead to progressive visual loss;
- **colitis**, characterized by inflammation of the gastrointestinal tract;
- **pneumonitis or CMV-associated lung disease**, with impaired respiratory function.

Among the different forms of transmission, congenital infection stands out, currently considered the main infectious cause of sensorineural hearing loss in childhood, with a significant impact on language development and quality of life of affected children.

CONGENITAL CMV INFECTION

CMV infection is in most cases asymptomatic when it occurs as a primary infection, reinfection, or reactivation, since these forms of infection are usually controlled by an intact immune system. However, CMV assumes significant clinical relevance in situations of immaturity or immune compromise, such as intrauterine infections, in which the fetus has an immune system that is still developing.

CMV is one of the most prevalent intrauterine infections worldwide. An overall seroprevalence of approximately 78–88% is estimated in the general population and 83–89% among women of childbearing age, with variations associated with socioeconomic and demographic factors (Zuhair et al., 2019).

The rate of vertical transmission varies according to maternal immune status. During primary infection, the risk of transmission to the fetus is between 24% and 40%. In non-primary infections, resulting from viral reactivation or reinfection by a different strain, the estimated risk is significantly lower, ranging from 0.5% to 2%.

The risk of maternal-fetal transmission of cytomegalovirus increases with older gestational age. At the same time, the severity of fetal clinical repercussions increases when the infection is acquired at earlier stages of pregnancy, so there is an inverse relationship between gestational age at the time of infection and the severity of clinical manifestations.

Mothers who have primary cytomegalovirus infection during pregnancy are more likely to transmit the virus to their fetus. On the other hand, secondary infection, resulting from viral reactivation or reinfection in women previously exposed to CMV before pregnancy, is usually associated with the birth of asymptomatic newborns. About 10% to 15% of newborns with CMV infection show clinical manifestations at birth.

However, approximately 25% of infected children develop some sequelae by the age of two,

showing that the absence of neonatal symptoms does not exclude the possibility of later involvement.

Although the prognosis is more favorable in cases that are asymptomatic at birth, about 13.5% of these children may develop permanent sequelae during follow-up.

**CMV causes congenital malformations in 1 in every 150 infected newborns.
Among the main complications are:**

- sensorineural hearing loss;
- microcephaly;
- developmental delays.

Following an initial infection with CMV, the virus remains in the host's body for life, establishing a state of latency. To date, there is no treatment capable of completely eradicating the virus, although the effectiveness of vaccination or passive immunization has been studied in some clinical trials. However, so far there are no vaccines to prevent or limit CMV infection in pregnant women. CMV can remain inactive, but it retains the ability to reactivate later, especially in people with compromised immune systems.

Although CMV infection is widely prevalent in the world's population, most immunocompetent individuals remain asymptomatic. Clinical manifestations are more frequently observed in individuals with impaired immune response. In this context, the importance of preventive strategies based on behavioral measures and education are considered fundamental for reducing the risk of maternal CMV infection during pregnancy.

In the next bulletin, the focus will be directed to the auditory aspects of individuals infected with CMV.

Quiz

1. To which viral family does cytomegalovirus (CMV) belong and what is one of its main biological characteristics?

- a) Retroviridae family, being a virus without an envelope and impossible to inactivate with 70% alcohol.
- b) Flaviviridae family, causing exclusively acute infections with no latency period.
- c) Herpesviridae family, being able to establish latent and recurrent infections throughout the host's life.
- d) Herpesviridae family, but it does not have a viral envelope, which makes it highly resistant to detergents.

2. In what type of individuals does cytomegalovirus infection usually cause more severe clinical manifestations and severe damage to target organs?

- a) In immunocompetent individuals during the first exposure to the virus.
- b) Exclusively in newborns who were infected after birth through breast milk.
- c) In any previously seronegative person, regardless of the effectiveness of their immune system.
- d) In individuals with compromised or immature immune systems, such as fetuses in intrauterine infections.

3. Regarding the vertical transmission of CMV during pregnancy, which of the following statements is correct?

- a) The probability of transmission of the virus from mother to fetus progressively decreases as gestational age advances.
- b) The risk of transmission to the fetus is substantially higher (between 24% and 40%) when the mother acquires the primary infection during pregnancy.
- c) Secondary infection (reactivation) has a risk of fetal transmission greater than 50%.
- d) The severity of clinical repercussions on the fetus tends to be greater when the infection occurs in the last trimester of pregnancy.

4. According to the text, what is the main long-term infectious complication associated with congenital cytomegalovirus infection in children?

- a) Severe retinitis soon after delivery.
- b) Sensorineural hearing loss.
- c) Chronic colitis with inflammation of the gastrointestinal tract.
- d) Progressive blindness in 100% of asymptomatic newborns.

5. Regarding the manifestation of symptoms and sequelae in newborns infected with CMV, it is correct to state that:

- a) All children infected with CMV have visible symptoms or evident clinical manifestations at the time of birth.
- b) Only symptomatic newborns are at risk of developing permanent sequelae throughout development.
- c) Auditory sequelae disappear naturally until the child reaches two years of age.
- d) The absence of symptoms at birth does not exclude the risk of the child developing late involvement.

REFERENCES CONSULTED

01. Griffiths P, Reeves M. Pathogenesis of human cytomegalovirus in the immunocompromised host. *Nat Rev Microbiol.* 2021; 19(12):759-73. doi: 10.1038/s41579-021-00582-z
02. Zuhair M, Smit G, Wallis G, Jabbar F, Smith C, Devleeschauwer B, et al. Estimation of the worldwide seroprevalence of cytomegalovirus: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Rev Med Virol.* 2019; 29(3):e2034. doi: 10.1002/rmv.2034
03. Boeckh M, Geballe AP. Cytomegalovirus: pathogen, paradigm, and puzzle. *J Clin Invest.* 2011; 121(5):1673-80. doi: 10.1172/JCI45449
04. Griffiths P, Baraniak I, Reeves M. The pathogenesis of human cytomegalovirus. *J Pathol.* 2015; 235(2):288-97. doi: 10.1002/path.4437
05. Kenneson A, Cannon MJ. Review and meta-analysis of the epidemiology of congenital cytomegalovirus (CMV) infection. *Rev Med Virol.* 2007; 17(4):253-76. doi: 10.1002/rmv.535
06. Dollard SC, Grosse SD, Ross DS. New estimates of the prevalence of neurological and sensory sequelae and mortality associated with congenital cytomegalovirus infection. *Rev Med Virol.* 2007; 17(5):355-63. doi: 10.1002/rmv.544
07. Manicklal S, Emery VC, Lazzarotto T, Boppana SB, Gupta RK. The "silent" global burden of congenital cytomegalovirus. *Clin Microbiol Rev.* 2013; 26(1):86-102. doi: 10.1128/CMR.00062-12
08. Ssentongo P, Hehnly C, Birungi P, Roach MA, Spady J, Fronterre C, et al. Congenital cytomegalovirus infection burden and epidemiologic risk factors in countries with universal screening. *JAMA Netw Open.* 2021; 4(8):e2120736. doi: 10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2021.20736
09. Rawlinson WD, Boppana SB, Fowler KB, Kimberlin DW, Lazzarotto T, Alain S, et al. Congenital cytomegalovirus infection in pregnancy and the neonate: consensus recommendations for prevention, diagnosis, and therapy. *Lancet Infect Dis.* 2017; 17(6):e177-88. doi: 10.1016/S1473-3099(17)30143-3
10. Carlson A, Norwitz ER, Stiller RJ. Cytomegalovirus infection in pregnancy: should all women be screened? *Rev Obstet Gynecol.* 2010; 3(4):172-9. PMC3046747
11. Pontes KFM, Nardoza LMM, Peixoto AB, Werner H, Tonni G, Granese R, et al. Cytomegalovirus and pregnancy: a narrative review. *J Clin Med.* 2024; 13(2):640. doi: 10.3390/jcm13020640
12. Maltezou PG, Kourlaba G, Kourkouni E, Luck S, Blazquez-Gamero D, Ville Y, et al. Maternal type of CMV infection and sequelae in infants with congenital CMV: systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Clin Virol.* 2020;131:104518. doi: 10.1016/j.jcv.2020.104518
13. Fowler KB. Congenital cytomegalovirus infection: audiologic outcome. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2013; 57(Suppl 4):S182-4. doi: 10.1093/cid/cit609
14. Boppana SB, Pinninti S, Britt WJ. Auditory and vestibular involvement in congenital cytomegalovirus infection. *Pathogens.* 2024; 13(11):1019. doi: 10.3390/pathogens13111019
15. Aldè M, Di Berardino F, Ambrosetti U, Binda S, Primache V, Pariani E, et al. Congenital cytomegalovirus and hearing loss: the state of the art. *J Clin Med.* 2023; 12(13):4465. doi: 10.3390/jcm12134465
16. Xia W, Yan H, Zhang Y, Wang C, Gao W, Lv C, et al. Congenital human cytomegalovirus infection inducing sensorineural hearing loss. *Front Microbiol.* 2021;12:649690. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2021.649690
17. Pesch MH, Schleiss MR. Emerging concepts in congenital cytomegalovirus. *Pediatrics.* 2022; 150(2):e2021055896. doi: 10.1542/peds.2021-055896
18. Schleiss MR, Pesch MH. Emerging concepts in congenital cytomegalovirus. *Pediatrics.* 2022; 150(2):e2021055896. doi: 10.1542/peds.2021-055896
19. Ross SA, Kimberlin DW. Clinical outcome and the role of antivirals in congenital cytomegalovirus infection. *Antiviral Res.* 2021;191:105083. doi: 10.1016/j.antiviral.2021.105083
20. Plotkin SA, Boppana SB. Vaccination against the human cytomegalovirus. *Vaccine.* 2019; 37(50):7437-42. doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2018.02.089

Correct answers:

1. Correct answers: C
2. Correct answers: D
3. Correct answers: B
4. Correct answers: B
5. Correct answers: D

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